

Effect of temperature and moisture on mechanical properties of a woven and short fibre thermoplastic composites for load-bearing automotive parts

R. Ourahmoune, M. Salvia, J. Laborde

Laboratoire de Tribologie et de Dynamique des Systèmes, Ecole Centrale de Lyon, 36 avenue Guy de Collongue, 69134, Ecully, France, Email: michelle.salvia@ec-lyon.fr, web page: <http://ltds.ec-lyon.fr>

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials with organic matrix can be a good alternative to replacement of classical metallic materials due in particular to their lightness associated to good mechanical properties (high specific modulus and stress at break). The weight saving has a direct impact on the surrounding, by the considerable decrease of emission of non-desirable gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂). In an economic context the use of mid-range materials is preferred in automotive mass production. In this context, E-glass fibre reinforced polyamide-6 (PA6) thermoplastic composites are good candidates. Recyclability of thermoplastics is one of their various advantages. PA6 is a semi-crystalline polymer characterized by acceptable mechanical properties such as ductility, good fatigue behaviour and resistance to chemicals and hydrocarbons. At comparable thickness and shape composite material parts based on PA6 reinforced with glass fibres are not equivalent to steels in terms of overall rigidity. In order to overcome this difficulty, a new technique of composite manufacturing was developed allowing to over-mould a continuous fibre reinforced PA6 stamped laminate with short fibre reinforced PA6 by injection moulding in the same tooling equipment at specific locations. The main objective of this work was to characterize the mechanical behaviour of the different zones of a complex over-moulded composite part: laminate, injected and over-moulded zones in relation with temperature (range 23 - 150°C) and the matrix moisture content (up to 8%) as polyamide 6 is more hygroscopic than most thermoplastics.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their excellent properties, fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites have been attracting considerable attention in recent years in the field of automotive industry. Their main advantages among structural materials are lightness (compared to metals) which reduces energy consumption and therefore engine emissions, toughness and recyclability (compared to thermosets). The choice of these materials represent an important step in the eco-design of automotive parts in the frame of an environmentally friendly approach. In this way, thermoforming process of thermoplastic laminates reinforced with continuous fibers associated with injection molding of discontinuous reinforced thermoplastic in order to add stiffeners or specific functions at precisely defined locations is increasingly used for applications which require structural lightweight parts. In this context, E-glass fibre reinforced polyamide-6 (PA6) thermoplastic composites are good candidates. PA6 is a semi-crystalline polymer characterized by good mechanical properties such as ductility and fatigue behaviour as well as good resistance to chemicals and hydrocarbons but it is more hygroscopic than most polymers [1-2].

The main objective of this work was to characterize the mechanical behaviour of the different zones of a complex over-moulded composite part: laminate, injected and over-moulded zones in relation with temperature (range 23 - 150°C) and the moisture content (up to 8%). In this aim a prototype structural part with a complex shape was designed in the frame of a collaborative research (Arizona FUI project).

The relaxation processes of composites were considered using DMA. The effect of temperature and moisture on the coefficients of the stiffness matrix and the properties at break such as stress at failure were investigated through tensile and flexural tests. For tensile tests, digital stereo correlation was used to calculate field strain. Acoustic emission (AE) was monitored during flexural tests performed at room temperature.

2 MATERIALS

A prototype part with a complex shape was designed by Mecaplast® group after shape optimization. The mold was made by the company Compose®. All prototype parts were manufactured at the PEP (Pôle Européen de Plasturgie,) [3-4] using two semi-finished Polyamide PA6 based composites supplied by Bond-Laminates GmbH® and Lanxess®:

- (1) a pre-consolidated sheet made with two 0.5 mm thick preimpregnated plies commercially available under the trade name Tepex® Dynalyte® 102 RG 600(2); the reinforcement is a twill balanced woven E-glass fabric.
- (2) a PA6 compound for injection reinforced with 60 percent by weight of discontinuous E-glass fibres with a nominal length of 250 μm ; this material, commercially named Durethan® BKV® 60, is made with the same grade of PA6 than Tepex® Dynalyte® 102 RG 600(2).

The process sequence was as follow (Figure 1): the pre-consolidated sheet (1mm thick) was pre-cut in the desired shape and orientation (long axis parallel to the warp direction) and then heated by an infrared furnace which ensured a homogenous temperature distribution in the laminate. The preheated composite was transferred from the furnace and inserted into the mold with the handling equipment in less than 20s. The forming of the lay-up was given by mold closing and compression and followed by the injection of ribs and multifunctional elements. The process was finished by demoulding and removal of the part.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of process manufacturing steps of composite part and optical micrograph showing an over-molded composite zone.

Temperature of pre-heating was 295°C above the melting temperature of the matrix (about 220°) in order to make the textile prepreg deformation possible. Mold temperature was 110°C.

Test specimens were obtained by water jet cutting from prototypes from three zones: (1) laminate zone (1 mm thick) named CGFR-PA6 (Figure 2a), (2) injected composite zone (3 mm thick) named DGFR-PA6 (Figure 2b), (3) overmoulded composite zone (4 mm thick: 1mm CGFR-PA6 and 3 mm DGFR-PA6) (Figure 1).

Figure 2: BSE mode micrographs showing polished section of: a) CGFR-PA6 and b) DGFR-PA6.

Table 1 summarizes the actual weight fraction, X_f (burn-out test) and the mean thermal properties determined (DSC1 device from METTLER-TOLEDO (Star® System) on as-machined DGFR-PA6 and CGFR-PA6 samples (5) randomly taken from the prototypes. For DSC analysis, the samples, each weighing approximately 10 mg, were small layers cut through the full wall thickness of the composites and then sealed in a DSC aluminum pan. The heating rate was 10K/min. The melting temperature (T_m) and the crystallinity rate (X_c) were measured and calculated from heat flow spectra. The melting

temperature was taken at the maximum of the endothermic peak of crystalline phase melting and the crystallinity rate X_c was calculated from the melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) of polymer according to the relationship (1) where (ΔH_{100}) is the enthalpy of fusion of 100 % crystalline PA6 (188 J/g [5]):

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{(1 - X_f) \Delta H_{100}} \quad (1)$$

Specimen	Melting temperature, T_m [°C]	Standard deviation [°C]	Crystallinity rate, X_c [%]	Standard deviation [%]	Fibre weight fraction, X_f
CGFR-PA6	222.5	1.3	40.2	1	0.64
DGFR-PA6	224	0.5	37.5	0.9	0.62

Table 1: Melting temperature and crystallinity rate (10 K/min).

3. METHODS

3.1 Dynamic mechanical analysis

Dynamical mechanical analysis (DMA) provides convenient and sensitive determination of thermo-mechanical properties of polymers and reinforced polymers at solid state as a function of frequency and temperature. It consists in either applying a sinusoidal force to a material and measuring the displacement or applying a displacement and measuring the displacement. The displacement is lagged behind the force by a phase angle δ due to the viscoelastic characteristics of the polymers [6]. From the force and displacement measurements the complex stiffness can be deduced, $K^* = K' + jK''$ where K' is the storage stiffness and K'' is the loss stiffness. The loss factor is the ratio of loss stiffness to storage stiffness $\tan \delta = K''/K'$. Knowing the sample geometry either complex tensile (E^*) or shear modulus (G^*) can be obtained depending on the deformation mode. This method is particularly appropriate to analyse the relaxation processes ((main) and sub-T_g) of polymer-based materials [7]. In this study, tests were performed on rectangular specimens (20mm×2mm× thickness mm) in tension-compression mode at controlled dynamic displacement ($\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$) in the linear viscoelasticity domain. Temperature sweep was carried out at a heating rate of 1 K/min in [-130 - 200 °C] temperature range. The measuring frequency was from 0.1 Hz to 30 Hz.

3.2 Tensile tests and Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

Monotonic tensile tests were performed using a hydraulic MTS tester equipped with a load cell of 100 kN and an oven (T_{max} : 350°C) at a cross-head speed of 2.54 mm/min and digital image stereo correlation (DISC) was used to determine in and out of displacements and strain maps on deformed surfaces [8] (Figure 3a). The correlation is possible only if the surface has a random texture. The specimens were painted with aerosol black and white spray paint on one face to create a speckle pattern with adequate contrast (Figure 3b). A region of interest (ROI) was defined on the specimen surface. The correlation algorithm compared gray level of each pixel in subset defined in the region of interest (ROI). Once the matching was done, the displacement components of the center of the reference and deformed subset can be determined. The strain field was then derived from the filtered displacement field. When using one camera, (2D-DIC) the temporal correlation takes only into account in plane displacements. To determine the position of an object in the three dimensions, two simultaneous images of the same object, with a different camera angle are needed. Digital image stereo correlation (DISC or 3D-DIC) combines temporal and stereoscopic matching. In this study, strain computation was carried out by Vic3D[®] software developed by Correlated Solutions[®].

The tests were carried out on the composite reinforced with continuous glass fiber (CGFR-PA6) oriented at [0/90°] or [$\pm 45^\circ$] to the loading direction. Specimen dimensions were 200 mm long, 25 mm wide and 1 mm thick (Figure 3c). For DGRP composites the sample dimensions were about 150*15*3mm³ and were taken in the edge of the part. Aluminum end-tabs were bonded on the ends of the tested specimens in order to minimize the stress concentration due to the tightening of grips.

Figure 3: (a) Tensile test and digital stereo-correlation device (b) Speckles on CGFR-PA6

3.3 Three-point bending tests and Acoustic emission

Three-point bending loadings were carried out using an electromechanical INSTRON machine (4206) equipped with a load cell of 5 kN and the cross-head speed was 2.5 mm/min. The radius of the load roller was 5 mm and the support span was 60 mm. Experimental procedure was made according to the International standard ISO 14125 at room temperature ($T=23\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 40\pm 5\%$). CGFR-PA6 samples had the following dimensions: 100 mm long, 25 mm wide and 1 mm thick. In the case of DGFR-PA6 and over-molded composite the samples dimensions were $100 \times 15 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ and $100 \times 15 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ respectively. DGFR-PA6 specimens were taken in two zones (edge: zone 1, top: zone 2) of the part. AE signals were monitored during monotonic bending tests using AE acquisition and analyzing system Mistras 2001 from Physical Acoustics Corporation (PAC). The AE signals were detected by a piezoelectric sensor (R15) attached to the sample by silicon grease and a mechanical specific device on the sample. The signals were amplified by a pre and a post-amplifier with a total gain of 70dB. The detection threshold of AE was fixed at 35dB. The amplitude of the signal was used because it is independent on the detection threshold. Several authors [9-10] have shown on different inorganic (glass or carbon) fibre reinforced composites that events with low amplitude (between 35–50 dB) are correlated with matrix microcracking, intermediate amplitude with delamination and microcracking coalescence (50-60dB) and matrix/fiber debonding (60-70 dB), high amplitude with fiber/matrix friction associated to pull-out (70-85 dB) and fiber breakages (>85 dB).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Material conditioning

The moisture absorption of water was achieved by immersion in distilled water at constant temperature ($T = 23^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). Specimens were previously dried for 8 days in a stove at 60°C , in the objective to remove all residual moisture due to air conditioning and transportation. For all studied composites the kinetics of water diffusion followed the one-dimensional Fick's second law. The apparent diffusion coefficient and the maximum moisture content in the matrix (it was assumed that only the matrix PA6 uptakes water) varied with the nature of composite. In continuous glass reinforced PA-6 composites the matrix achieved moisture saturation at about 8.7% with an apparent coefficient of water diffusion equal to $7.01 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ whereas discontinuous glass reinforced PA-6 composite (DGFR-PA6) showed better hygrothermal properties since the water diffusivity and the moisture content at saturation were lower than for the CGFR-PA6 ($M_\infty = 7.7\%$ and $D = 5.1 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$), probably due to random architecture of fibers which constitutes a physical barrier to water diffusion in the matrix. Conditioned specimens were obtained using these parameters.

4.2 Thermomechanical properties

The temperature and frequency dependences of E' and $\tan \delta$ for dry and wet (8 % in matrix) [$\pm 45^\circ\text{C}$] CGFR-PA6 are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Loss factor $\tan \delta$ and storage tensile modulus, E' for dry and wet (8 % in matrix) $[\pm 45^\circ\text{C}]$ CGFR-PA6.

In the range of temperature studied (-130; 200 °C) a decrease of storage modulus was observed with temperature increase. The structural change occurring in polymeric materials was a result of the molecular mobility at different time scales. These motions were known as molecular relaxations. In the case of dried PA6 based composites three clear relaxations can be distinguished [2]:

- the main relaxation or α -relaxation corresponding to the drastically decrease of the storage modulus and the highest peak of $\tan \delta$; this relaxation was associated to the glass transition, and corresponded to coordinated motion of relatively long chain segments by debonding of low energy bonds (hydrogen bonds). This relaxation occurred at $T_\alpha = 90^\circ\text{C}$ (10 Hz).
- two sub-Tg relaxations: the β -relaxation and γ -relaxation corresponding to the motions of small chain segments or molecular functions. The β -relaxation involved the rotation of the amide functions and occurred in the range of -80 /-40°C depending on frequency; the γ -relaxation corresponded to the vibrational motions of the methylene functions in the chains and it occurred at around -130°C.

After conditioning by water immersion, the DMA results showed that the presence of water in the PA6 matrix involved a shift of the mechanical molecular relaxations to lower temperature as observed in Figure 4. In particular, the T_α decreases from 90°C in dry composite to 0°C for wet composite at 10 Hz due to plasticizing effect of water.

4.3 Effect of temperature and moisture on tensile behavior

Mechanical behavior of dry conditioned samples was analyzed at four temperatures: 25, 40, 80 and 130°C. Three moisture levels in matrix were tested: dry, 3, 5 and 8 % (7.5 % for DGFR-PA6) at room temperature. The strains were calculated according the two major directions e_1 : following the loading direction and e_2 perpendicular to the loading direction using digital stereo correlation as given in Figure 5 which shows an example of the evolution of strain map as a function of stress increase for dry $[0/90^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6.

Figure 5: Tensile test on for dry $[0/90^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6: (a) in plane strain map as a function of stress; (b) definition of directions; (c) stress-strain curve

The tensile modulus was calculated from the slope between the calculated strain and the stress in the linear region. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) was taken as the maximal stress before breakage.

Stress-strain curve, tensile modulus (E_1) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) obtained on $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6 versus temperature and moisture were presented in Figures 6 and 7 respectively. At various temperatures dry conditioned specimens showed a classical slightly non-linear behavior for woven fabric composites with a knee point around strain $\epsilon_1 \sim 4\%$ which was associated to initial transverse matrix cracks [11]. A moderate decrease in tensile modulus was observed with temperature rise ($\sim 7\%$). For this stacking sequence, the longitudinal modulus is mainly fiber-dominated, even if for woven composite, the waviness of the fibre bundles have some importance [12]. Unlike modulus, the tensile ultimate strength decreased approximately 22% when the test temperature increased from room temperature to 130°C . This sharp decrease was caused by the softening of the resin matrix when glass transition temperature of PA6 zone was reached (section 4.2) resulting in a loss in the efficiency of load transfer between the matrix and the glass fibre. The behavior of the composite was not significantly affected by moisture until around 3% after which a drop in modulus and UTC was observed ($\sim 22\%$.) The decrease in mechanical properties of woven composite was probably associated at the early stages to the matrix modulus drop as a function of moisture as shown in section 4.2 and then to a decrease of interfacial strength. A hydrolytic damage of glass fibre at highest moisture level may not be excluded [13].

Figure 6. $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6: influence of temperature on tensile behavior: (a) stress-strain curves; (b) tensile modulus and ultimate strength vs T

Figure 7: $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6: influence of matrix moisture content on tensile behavior: (a) stress-strain curves; (b) tensile modulus and ultimate strength vs moisture content

The tensile behavior of DGFR-PA6 versus test temperature and moisture content was presented in Figures 9 and 10 respectively. The results showed a highly non-linear behavior which was matrix-dominated. The tensile modulus and UTS appeared to decrease about 60% and 52%, respectively with the test temperature increase from 25°C to 130°C . This phenomenon was associated to glass transition leading to a lowering of matrix and interface properties. Same results were observed as a function of matrix moisture. The tensile modulus and the UTS for wet specimens (8%) decreased about 55% and

45%, respectively, relative to dry specimens. The water acts as a plasticizer and could have a detrimental effect on interface fibre/matrix strength. Therefore, tensile stiffness and strength of DGFR-PA6 composite materials are lowered.

Figure 9: DGFR-PA6: influence of temperature on tensile behavior: (a) stress-strain curves; (b) tensile modulus and ultimate strength vs T

Figure 10: DGFR-PA6: influence of matrix moisture content on tensile behavior: (a) stress-strain curves; (b) tensile modulus and ultimate strength vs moisture content

The tensile behavior of $[\pm 45^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6 laminates versus matrix moisture content was presented in Figure 11a. Same highly non-linear behavior was observed as a function of temperature. It is clear that $[\pm 45^\circ]$ tensile behavior was mainly driven by matrix property. The stress-strain showed a short linear part from which the shear modulus G_{12} was determined followed by a highly nonlinear zone. The shear modulus G_{12} according to temperature and moisture decreased associated to the softening of the matrix due to glass transition or plasticization as mentioned previously.

Figure 11: $[\pm 45^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6: (a) influence of matrix moisture content on tensile behavior stress-strain curves; (b) shear modulus G_{12} vs moisture content and temperature

Poisson's ratio was measured from the linear region of the transverse strain versus longitudinal strain graph obtained with DISC for all studied composites (Figure 12). All the composites with $[\pm 45^\circ]$ stacking sequence had a Poisson's ratio higher than composites with $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ stacking sequence and discontinuous fibre reinforced composites. Results in Figure 12 exhibited that temperature and moisture had no significant effect on $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$. As expected, Poisson's ratio for $[\pm 45^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6 and DGFR-PA6 was driven by matrix property as it increased with temperature and moisture content increase.

Figure 12: Poisson's ratio: (a) influence of matrix moisture content; (b) influence of temperature

4.4 Effect of moisture on flexural properties

Flexural mechanical properties of all composites according moisture content were studied using 3-point bending test. For CGFR-PA6, only $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ stacking sequence was tested. For DGFR-PA6 composites two zones were analyzed (zone 1: edge; zone 2: top) which differed in fibre orientation (Figure 13). Moreover, due to the multi-layering feature of over-moulded composites, two bending configurations were investigated: in the first, the continuous glass fibers were on the tensile side and in the second on the compressive side

Figure 13: BSE micrographs showing post mortem failure of DGFR-PA6 taken from (a) zone 1 (oriented fibre) and (b) zone 2 (Skin/core morphology)

The linear part of the stress-strain curve corresponded to the apparent bending elastic modulus (homogenized moduli for over-moulded composites) (E_f) and the ultimate bending stress was taken as the maximal stress of the stress-strain curve (σ_{max}).

Figure 14 illustrated the evolution of apparent bending modulus (a) and ultimate bending strength (b) as a function of moisture content for all studied composites. The results showed a sharp decrease in bending modulus as well as in ultimate bending strength for all composites. These results were coherent with those obtained in tension mode.

For example, the continuous glass fibres reinforced PA6 (CGFR-PA6) exhibited a decrease of 50% in both bending properties for the highest moisture content state. At 5% of moisture content the modulus tended to reduce by about 50% and strength decreased approximately 36%. No macroscopic failure was

observed on the tensile side but few micro-damages occurred in the central zone. The composites showed mainly kink band failures on the compressive side especially in the case of wet composites.

Figure 14: Evolution of flexural properties according to the moisture content for all composites: a) apparent bending modulus and b) ultimate bending stress.

Acoustic emission activity allowed distinguishing different damage mechanisms for these composites at dry and wet (4%) states (Figure 15). The wet specimens (Figure 15b) presented AE signals which showed that damage initiation and propagation in an aged material was different from the dry composite (Figure 15a). There was a progressive damage of the wet specimen and many discontinuities appeared on the stress-strain curve. The dry specimen (Figure 15a) exhibited amplitude histogram with two peaks. The low amplitude AE (below 60 dB) broad peak was due to matrix microcracking and fibre/matrix micro-debonding, whereas the middle range amplitude hits accounted for the second peak (between 60 and 85 dB) were associated to pull-out phenomenon. Some AE events of high amplitude (85-100 dB) were also revealed suggesting breakage of fibers, the interface fiber/matrix being strong enough to transfer stresses from matrix to fiber. For wet composites AE amplitudes were mainly distributed between 35 dB and 60 dB (Figure 15b). This may confirm matrix and fiber/matrix interface weakening by the water absorption finally causing fiber micro-buckling which was governed by the matrix shear modulus occurring on the compressive side (Figure 16) and plastic deformation without any pull-out on the tensile side.

Figure 15: AE hits versus amplitude during 3-point bending test on $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ CGFR-PA6: a) dry composite and b) wet composite $M(t) = 4\%$,

Figure 16: Wet [0°/90°] CGFR-PA6: SEM analysis of kink band failures on the compressive side

5. CONCLUSION

In this study the thermomechanical and mechanical properties of PA6 based composites was investigated. This work demonstrated that the conditioning history and environment temperature are important parameters to be taken into account in design of structural part composites based on PA6. In this aim a prototype structural part with a complex shape was designed in the frame of a collaborative research (Arizona FUI project). DMA were carried out on the composites and test results showed that the alpha-relaxation associated to glass transition is greatly affected by the presence of water (shift from 80°C (dry) to 0°C (8 % water content)). The effect of temperature and moisture on the coefficients of the stiffness matrix and the properties at break such as the stress at failure were investigated through tensile and flexural tests. For tensile tests, digital stereo correlation was used to calculate field strain. The stress-strain curve was significantly influenced by the temperature and moisture content for the highest levels especially for discontinuous fibre reinforced composites and [±45] laminates. Acoustic emission (AE) was monitored during flexural tests performed at room temperature. The number of events greatly decreases with ageing: this may be related to fibre/matrix interface weakening and matrix plasticization due to water absorption.

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